

TECHNIQUES FOR ENHANCING STUDENTS’ PROFESSIONAL SKILLS VIA DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES

Kurbonov Gulomjon Gafurovich

Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute, Associate Professor of the Department of Exact
Sciences, (PhD)

gulomjonqurbanov0880@gmail.com

Abstract. This article describes the creation of a mobile application and a web application for the subject of "Entering the Specialty" in order to make it more convenient for students. This web application combines online education and distance education. This article depicts how students, through the web application, independent learners, and users of the system can independently strengthen their knowledge, skills, and abilities, develop their interests, and improve their level of knowledge.

Keywords. digital technology, digitalization, digital educational technologies, LMS, CMS, mobile education, web-application distance education, electro-didactic, visual information, conception, metacognitive.

INTRODUCTION

In these days, teaching and learning are essential matter. Good education plays an important role in saving us from the various problems we are facing. That is why all developing countries are spending a lot of money on improving the quality of education.

Despite this, there are a number of problems that have not yet been solved in the education system. However, in today's era, when the speed of obtaining and using information is very fast, it is impossible to improve the quality of education and educate socially active young people without involving digital technologies in the educational system. Most of the educational programs are conducted in the form of lectures, and the educational process is carried out with the use of large volumes of books and manuals. After coming to the present day, the educational digitization process started. Also, the educational process is improved by creating modern facilities for students.

Free access to digital educational technologies for the content of higher education creates great opportunities for the development of the educational process, taking into account the individual abilities of each student. Consequentially, many textbooks are being digitized at the request of users, and they are organizing special courses.

According to the goal set before us, there are two types of software programs, systematic and practical programs, and in this case, programs used in the educational process (electronic textbooks and manuals, mobile Improvement of students' knowledge), support and skills was carried out using such software as LMS (Learning Management Systems), CMS (Content Management Systems) and educational management systems.

MAIN PART

A Content Management System (CMS) is a collection of software tools that help users create, manage, and modify website content without technical knowledge. In other words, CMS allows us to create a website without the need to write software code. This helps to save a lot of time, technical equipment, eyes, storage, and storage space. In this way, it is possible to achieve a clear goal (look at the first picture).

It is possible to integrate digital technologies into the educational process in the following ways: students can use it as a tool to organize independent projects in the auditory and outside time. This version of it makes it easier to check for teachers. (They don't spare time to check.) Similarly, over time, the learner can get information about how long and often they read the news, what kind of information they refer to, and how much the learning process has changed in a positive way.

Picture 1. Achievements achieved through the content management system

The problem of how to develop and present mobile educational software to the public is considered to be an urgent issue in the educational market today. Ongoing studies have shown that mobile learning software is highly effective and user-friendly, and they highlight the following important factors:

- It is a good idea to prepare mobile learning programs, and it means a 60–70 percent success rate. It is possible to prepare a competitive program in the market based on this idea;

- In the process of conducting research, it is important to study the mobile education market, to prepare and use all three parameters;

- preparation of mobile educational programs, conducting workshops in small groups, and taking into account the recommendations of experienced pedagogues;

- Mobile educational software users should turn to software engineers who are engaged in the research and development of services, development companies, and processes [1].

In addition to the digital analysis in the field of ICT, demand and supply are presented to the users through a clear and understandable database, and the development of the development theories is also carried out, as we will see. Interestingly, we can see how mobile learning can lead to three types of educational independence for learners. Taking into account the students' functional, psychological, and physiological abilities, they form the skills and abilities of independent education through the use of formal educational tools.

Higher education 60110700 - "Mathematics and Informatics" education students, using digital technologies as a virtual environment in teaching, to solve the following 4 (four) problems:

- students are able to individually master the subjects of independent education allocated to the subject;

- to emphasize that there will be no distance and time limits in the process of education;

- distance education is more interesting for users than usual;

- attention is paid to the existence of a separate mobile application for the use of the virtual class of science [2].

When previous problems are solved, modern educational professors-teachers in the field of education develop the possibilities of effective use of digital technologies in the course of teaching.

In the process of development, various scientific approaches to the development of mobile educational methods and educational-technical development are being considered, and problems are being eliminated.

In the process of developing electro-didactic forms of education, the abilities and interests of students are taken into account. A professor-teacher who is involved in the implementation of educational content, educational goals and pedagogy, digital technological methods, and teaching methods between students is involved in complex interactions [3].

Depending on the level of coverage of educational content, goals, and tasks, the possibility of applying electronic educational resources to the educational process will appear.

About the currently developing mobile education, the Great British scientist S.Trongtor gave a general description of mobile education in his scientific work. Mobile education students [4] have developed educational methods using mobile phones, smartphones, tablets, computers, and portable devices that help in the development of all three methods. Mobile educational technologies are used for the purpose of improving, supporting, and improving the educational process so that it can be attractive to teachers and students.

Mobile education helps students actively participate in the individual approach to solving the problems of the system in the most accessible, useful, relevant, and stimulating ways. In order to adapt to mobile education, teachers who are active at all levels of education need to use modern technologies and software tools to use mobile education in the educational process. However, we know that there are some problems with this process even in societies with a good social and economic environment. They include such issues as teaching methodology development and the appropriate applications for teachers, as well as the use of mobile education and the development of competence [5].

Therefore, it is necessary to study the requirements and principles of remote, mobile education based on the requirements of the educational process.

Based on the mentioned principles, digital educational materials are prepared in the orderly preparation of audio, video, and physical data, as well as normative documents. Students have the ability to receive visual information and provide simple, clear, and understandable information on the topic. In this case, it is necessary to take into account the interrelationships between educational resources [88]. Due to the rapid development of digital educational technologies in today's world, the above principles are self-explanatory, and these changes have been studied [6].

Based on the above-mentioned principles of foreign scientists, mobile education should follow the following principles:

- it is possible to use different methods of information presentation, and it is shown that it helps to visualize complex processes and events in a way that cannot be imagined in real life;
- it is necessary to place one cooperative element on one interface as much as possible in a related format. This allows the user to learn the object (process, event) in various aspects and all kinds of methods;
- information such as audio, graphics, and text should be used for visualization. This user can create an external load, for example, an object (process, event) in a multi-dimensional way.

- it is necessary to match the educational content with the goals and tasks of the educational program in the form of mobile educational materials;
- it is necessary to consider the knowledge and cognitive characteristics of students;
- it is necessary to take a pedagogical-psychological approach to the use of mobile educational materials in the form of text, visual, and audio presentations at the same time;
- complex concepts and processes are presented through a single medium, or through two or more information-presenting mass media;
- students should have a high level of metacognitive abilities, make connections through hyper math, and find all kinds of information properly [7].

Pedagogical experiences using the above-mentioned principles of mobile education are shown in the teaching of general and special education "Information systems, mathematics, and software education" in higher education institutions using digital technologies. It is of great importance for the improvement of efficiency. In this regard, mobile educational tools play an important role [8].

In this area, higher education institutions 60110700 “Mathematics and Informatics” curriculum, “Introduction to Specialization”, is used to prepare students for professional activity, which plays an important role in.

In the “Entry to Specialization” activity, the teacher not only mentions the main goals of the course but also explains the requirements for each level. The sequence of tasks executed in software development and the practical instruction of the methods of their execution are virtually suitable for students in independent schools. The advantage of this method is that the teacher has the opportunity to devote time to students who do not know the subject well and give them practical help. As a result, it is possible to monitor the students' ability to complete the tasks correctly and their understanding. There are three methodological guidelines for the implementation of practical training tasks, which are as follows: the purpose, the necessary information for the implementation of the task, the requirements for the tasks to be demonstrated, and the independent practical tasks and checking tests.

Access to the specialty is based on the use of mobile software called "E-Learning" (electronic learning). "E-learning" (electrical education) is technology that combines online education and distance education. This mobile program allows students and independent teachers to strengthen their training in the three auditory areas, to make their own decisions, to set their own rates, and to use them at their own convenience without using mobile phones or smartphones. It creates 75–90% more energy.

In addition, in mobile and web applications, all contents are available, as well as lecture and practical training topics, explanatory information, glossaries, tasks for

independent performance, a block of tests, practical solutions to the exercises, videos, virtual boards, a list of useful literature, and brief information about the author.

In order to make it more convenient for students, we have created a web application for the sub-subject "Entering the specialty" This web application combines online education and distance education. Through the web application, students, independent learners, and users of the system can independently strengthen their knowledge, skills, and abilities, develop their interests, and improve their level of knowledge.

In the course of the conducted research, the educational program is highly effective, the process of delivery to the users is studied, and it is based on the following important factors:

- a prepared web app is the best one.
- in the process of conducting research, it is important that all the parameters of the web application educational market are studied and prepared by the user;
- preparation of web application educational programs, conducting workshops in small groups, and taking into account the recommendations of experienced pedagogues are so important;
- the web application is intended for use by users of educational programs, development services, research organizations, research and process programming practices, and professional developers;

This web application is integrated with the mobile application mentioned above, and users can access these applications through different browsers or mobile devices. When using the application, you can see all the information about them in two ways.

The user interface is organized into five functions, such as registration, access to the system, access to the forum, information about the author, e-books, and user knowledge control. Users need to be registered in the system in order to use opportunities. In the entry section, full information about the site will be provided, and users will be able to familiarize themselves with the site's content.

Through the Author profile, users can get information about the creator of the application and contact the author in case of problems. In the literature section, refer to relevant literature and references.

In the course of the lessons, there are topics related to the subject, and every test will be completed by the users in each specific area. After studying the first topic completely, there are tests related to the theme. It provides audio, video, and additional information to help the user. After the user has completely selected the above-mentioned sections, he should refer to the topic of this topic. The student will be given 25 tests, and if he gets a score of 60% or higher, he will be able to enroll in a specific topic and study the following topics. After successfully completing the test, users can move on to the next topic; otherwise, this topic will need to be changed

again. Communication between the user and the teacher is carried out by telegram and e-mail.

CONCLUSION

“Entry to the Specialization” aims to attract students to special educational events that help them develop their own knowledge and skills and take an active role in the process of acquiring knowledge and participating in competitions. Advanced methods (educational preparation and organization of exhibitions, creation of models, case-methods, meetings with experts, and others), promotional methods (bright, eye-catching illustrations and memorable sentences are highly emotional and psychological for students, opportunities training), and others.

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